

The Role of Marketing in Businesses and Methods of Implementing Innovations

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Abstract: Marketing plays a key role in the success of companies, even the most famous ones. Systematization of branding, marketing and customer relations give great results. This article examines marketing using examples of large companies such as Coca-Cola, Apple, and others to show their methods and actions, research that are applied to global economic changes in the world and the 21st century today.

Keywords: Marketing, branding, major companies, research, business, innovation, commercialization, brand, AI in marketing, technology.

Introduction

Marketing is a set of strategies, goals, objectives and methods for creating a product, promoting it and organizing sales, as well as establishing contact with customers, employees, suppliers and partners. It is important to take into account that such a set is primarily aimed at obtaining benefits for the company. Marketing in practical terms implies the processes of stimulating product sales, improving it, pricing policy, determining distribution channels and distributing advertising. For marketing activities, it is important to produce a product that will be in demand among consumers and will bring profit to the company. The goal of marketing is to cover the changing needs of target audience segments. The main task of marketing will be the choice of the market segment that the company can enter in order to produce goods and services of better quality and with less competition. This will allow the company to receive greater sales and profits.

Branding is the creation of a positive image of a company, its distribution and fixation in the client's mind. In simple terms, it is brand management. A brand is a trademark, a company's logo and its name. Branding includes a whole range of marketing activities to develop an image and strengthen long-term relationships with the consumer. Thanks to it, a unique style is created, the value of the product is increased and trust in the company is formed.

A clear illustration of why branding is so important is examples that are known all over the world - Apple, Ikea, Coca-Cola, Google. Consumers know these names and can immediately say what products the companies offer on the market and why they have received such popularity and love. And this depends on how companies position themselves on the market and what emotions they evoke in consumers.

Every year, Coca-Cola launches a New Year's advertisement with a melody that is recognizable from the first notes, it always flashes the famous truck that brings treats and gifts from the company. This video is associated with the feeling of celebration and a cozy evening with friends or loved ones.[3 Coca-Cola, 2023].

Literature reviews

This article will consider the research and information that is based in scientific publications such as - **1** Kotler & Keller, 2016, which tells what marketing is and methods, marketing strategies with action examples

2 in the informational publication Coca-Cola, 2023, examples and actions of marketing are taken and how global companies can influence the choice of buyers by giving them emotions and a desire to purchase a product of any company

3 Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019 - provides information on trends, innovations and technologies of modern marketing and how the algorithms of the system work, for example, such as targeting, and also opens up an idea of future events in the field of digital marketing

4 And about attracting customers as well as creating loyalty programs is described in the publication Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019, which gives examples of strategies and options that can attract and retain customers

Research methods

Here the primary research method was applied, or more precisely, information from official sources and publishers, analysis of the results of companies that used these or similar methods. The study also used the results of analyses of advertising strategies and their effectiveness.

The main role of marketing in business

1 Branding Understanding the opportunities that brands provide leads to the fact that they are used in almost all areas of human activity. The existing types of branding are simply amazing. This is used by all companies, from the smallest to the largest, and it is also used in the vast consumer sector such as B2B. For example, such huge companies as Coca-Cola and Apple use the above strategy as one of the most important, giving customers emotions and a desire to make even more purchases. [4 Kotler & Keller,2016].

2 Indication - brand positioning This is one of the main element in marketing strategies that focuses on distinguishing certain brand from other competitors and making it the most memorable of all of them . We can say that positioning is a figurative shell, a way of conveying brand ideas through various means. It must correspond to all interactions between the company and customers such as design, name, etc.

3 Personalization

Personalization it is also a part of marketing through which marketers develop an individual approach to each client and buyer separately. The offer may be a mailing list, landing page, catalog selection, discount size, content recommendations. 90% of companies are already investing in personalization, and for good reason: this is how businesses get to know their customers and predict what products they need. Offers become popular, and customers buy. [2 Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019].

Information system and technologies in modern marketing

Analysis of real practices of implementing digital solutions in business processes of enterprises shows that, focusing on consumer solutions, marketing services were among the first to master new tools for working in digital conditions. New promotion channels, a new audience with its own specific habits, new requirements for organizing marketing activities -

all this is already another technology-oriented reality in which modern businesses of different scales and spheres of activity operate, for example, such methods are used by the Apple company. Which collects data and information about the preferences of their users and, based on this, they generate innovations for their products [1 Apple, 2023].

Marketing and strategies in large company

Personalization and marketing of the Coca-Cola company .

This company used a unique strategy due to which their sales doubled. They introduced changes in packaging and added names of people there . Namely those names that are most often used in certain countries where this product is sold (they used targeting to collect more accurate information about their customers and which names are used more often) , then they included in their strategy the idea of engaging young people-they provided a promotion that those who share information about the product on social networks. Then their chances for a valuable prize were higher-valuable prizes such as equipment, acquaintance with a celebrity, cash prizes, as well as promotions that are valid for a year related to their products.

Moreover, Coca-Cola is one of the most successful companies because it constantly adapts its new products to the tastes and desires of people, thereby refreshing opinions about them and their products . [3 Coca-Cola, 2023].

Recomedations

The recommendation contains an idea for the introduction of artificial intelligence in the development and management of marketing , in the 21st century it is necessary to keep up with the times to stay afloat and overtake competitors. As well as for the success of not only marketing but also business in general, technologies and innovations are significantly important , in the case of marketing . One of the best innovations will be the introduction and use of artificial intelligence .

Important is the synchronization of marketing advertising with artificial intelligence. That is, in more detail, this is the collection of data about customers through artificial intelligence. This will greatly help to learn the needs and desires of customers in more detail than it would be without artificial intelligence, moreover, based on the collected information, artificial intelligence can generate a design or plan for a marketing strategy that is better suited or will give examples of suitable content. As mentioned before, this will give a chance to collect more accurate information about clients and knowing all the details we will be able to create a request in artificial intelligence on client loyalty, which also gives great advantages, it saves time and the most important thing is detail and accuracy.

Reference list –

Reference list

1. Apple (2024). *Apple*. [online] Apple. Available at: <https://www.apple.com/>.
2. Chaffey, D., Ellis-Chadwick, F., Isaac, H. and mercanti-guérin, M. (2014). *Marketing Digital*. [online] ResearchGate. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321125707_Marketing_Digital.
3. Coca-Cola (2024). *Coca-Cola Reports Fourth Quarter and Full Year 2023 Results*. [online] www.coca-colacompany.com. Available at: <https://www.coca-colacompany.com/media-center/fourth-quarter-full-year-2023-results>.
4. www.pearson.com. (2021). *Kotler and Keller, Marketing Management, Global Edition, 16th Edition*. [online] Available at: <https://www.pearson.com/se/Nordics-Higher-Education/subject-catalogue/marketing/Kotler-Keller-Marketing-Management-Global-Edition-16e.html>.